

Unveiling the Electronic Band Structure and Temporal Dynamics of Excited Carriers in Formamidinium Lead Bromide Perovskite

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Abstract

In this study, we have investigated the electronic band structure and the dynamics of the excited carriers in the formamidinium lead bromide (FAPbBr₃) perovskite combining the information obtained by steady-state absorption, photoluminescence, femtosecond transient absorption spectroscopy, photoelectron spectroscopy and density functional theory calculations. A detailed description of the electronic transitions in the UV-Vis energy range has been provided, giving an estimation of the exciton binding energy (40 ± 5 meV), the transition energy from the first valence band (VB1) to the conduction band (CB1) (electronic band gap at 2.37 ± 0.01 eV) and assigning the broad peak at about 3.4 eV to the transition from the second innermost valence band (VB2) to CB1. The temporal dynamics of the excited carriers involved in these transitions were investigated by different excitation energies and carrier densities. Different trends were observed in the dynamics of the transient signals associated with the VB1→CB1 (PB1) and VB2→CB1 (PB2) transitions. As the carrier density increased, PB1 exhibited a slowdown in its rise time, while PB2 showed an acceleration attributed to the thermalization of the excited holes in VB2. These valuable findings have the potential to unlock new strategies aimed at maximizing the efficiencies and performance of perovskite-based solar cell devices.

Keywords. Perovskite, band structure, ultrafast, carrier dynamics, photoelectron spectroscopy, multi-band, high-energy carriers

In recent years, hybrid perovskites¹ have triggered the interest of the scientific community because of their remarkable properties including high absorption coefficients in the visible range ($\alpha > 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)², ultralong carrier diffusion lengths³, long carrier lifetimes³, unusually high defect tolerances⁴ and bandgap tunability⁵⁻⁷. These properties make them suitable for a broad range of optoelectronic applications such as lasers^{8,9}, Light Emitting Diodes^{9,10}, photodetectors^{11,12}, and solar cells^{13,14}. The large bandgap of lead bromide perovskites (approximately 2.3 eV) is particularly appropriate for tandem applications and efficient semitransparent solar cells¹⁵⁻¹⁷. In this class of perovskites, formamidinium lead bromide (FAPbBr₃) is one of the most promising adsorbing materials because it shows high stability under light exposure¹⁸ and high carrier diffusion length that is compatible with a simple planar heterojunction solar cell configuration¹⁸⁻²¹. In spite of the proven superiority of the FAPbBr₃ in terms of semitransparency and stability, only few experimental²¹⁻²⁷ and theoretical studies^{25,28-30} have been performed to investigate its energetic and dynamics features. Therefore, a comprehensive understanding of the electronic and optical properties of FAPbBr₃ is of utmost importance for developing advanced solar applications based on this material.

Indeed, during the operation of the solar cell the carrier dynamics within the active perovskite material are influenced by different processes such as carrier thermalization³¹, cooling^{31,32}, and recombination^{10,33}. These features can provide important insights for the improvement of the materials and devices performances³⁴.

To gain insights into the optical properties and electronic structure of FAPbBr₃, photoelectron spectroscopy (PES) and femtosecond transient absorption spectroscopy (FTAS) were employed in synergy with advanced theoretical methods. PES allows the measurement of the electronic structure, energy levels, and band alignment of FAPbBr₃, providing crucial information for device optimization and design. On the other hand, FTAS permits the investigation of the carrier dynamics and relaxation processes in the perovskite, thus gaining valuable insights into the thermal relaxation and recombination pathways of the carriers in this material. To the best of our knowledge, excited-state energetics and dynamics of FAPbBr₃ remain still largely unexplored²², making the characterization of the excited-state dynamics of high bandgap perovskites timely to optimize the optical properties of these materials, because their performances directly depend on the generation and recombination of the charges. Furthermore, an in-depth understanding of the optical transitions and the electronic structures of the bands involved in the energy range covered by sun light, will assist the design of new generation photovoltaic materials with tailored optoelectronic features.

In the present work, the excited-state properties of a thin film of FAPbBr₃ have been studied combining steady-state absorption, photoluminescence (PL), FTAS, PES with density functional theory (DFT) calculations. In this way, we give a complete description of the electronic properties of FAPbBr₃, assigning the electronic bands involved in the photoexcitation by UV-Vis radiation and the related carrier dynamics, giving valuable

insights that pave the way for exploring novel strategies and design approaches to maximize the quality and performance of this material for photovoltaic applications. In fact, the study of the dynamics associated with the first valence band to first conduction band and the second valence band to the first conduction band transitions yield information on the lifetimes and energies of the excited charges. The analysis presented here shows that long-lived high-energy holes can be formed even at low carrier densities. Implications of these observations are discussed in the text.

Results and discussion

The absorbance spectrum of FAPbBr₃, reported in **Figure 1a** (solid orange line), shows an absorption peak at 2.32 eV and a shoulder at about 3.3-3.4 eV (see arrow) that is also visible in the first derivative of the same spectrum, as shown in **Figure S1** in the Supporting Information (SI). In the same figure the PL spectrum is shown for comparison (dashed orange line) but it only shows a single clear peak centered at 2.29 eV which is due to radiative exciton recombination.

Figure 1: a) Absorbance (solid line) and PL (dashed line) at room temperature of FAPbBr₃; the orange arrow at 3.4 eV highlights the second absorption structure. b) Experimental steady-state absorption of the FAPbBr₃ film (orange scatter), the fit using the Elliott model (orange line) and the relative decomposition of the Elliott fit into the contribution of the continuous states (red line) and the excitonic contribution (black line). The excitonic contributions to the absorption are simulated using three excitonic states ($n=1,2,3$) and are shown as blue lines.

Figure 1b shows the absorption spectrum in the photon energy range of 2.2-2.5 eV in which the sub-band gap intensity is set to zero to remove the scattering contribution to the spectrum. Overlaid on this spectrum is the best fit obtained using the Elliott model^{35,36} (see detail in the **Section S2** in SI) employed to evaluate the excitonic and continuum contributions to estimate the electronic bandgap of FAPbBr₃. From this fitting procedure an exciton binding energy of 40 ± 5 meV and an electronic bandgap of 2.37 ± 0.01 eV were estimated^{37,38}. The fit procedure takes into account an excitonic contribution due to excitons with $n=1, 2$ and 3 . The exciton binding energy extracted by the fit is larger than the value obtained by magnetoluminescence, which has been found to be about 25 meV²⁷.

Figure 2: Absorbance spectra (orange solid line) and transient absorption spectra at the pump photon energy of 3.85 eV, fluence of 50 $\mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$ and at the selected delay time of 2 ps (blue solid line) obtained for FAPbBr₃.

These results are confirmed by the transient absorption (TA) spectra obtained exciting the perovskite film with a photon energy of 3.85 eV. In fact, the TA spectrum reported in **Figure 2** (blue line) shows two photobleaching (PB) features at energies corresponding to the structures observed in the steady-state absorption. The first one (PB1), is found at 2.30 eV, close to the maximum of the exciton absorption, and the second one (PB2) is located at about 3.40 eV, in the same energy region of the above-mentioned shoulder present in the absorption spectrum. The TA measurement allows for a more evident determination of the spectral features in the absorption; the energy difference between these two features that is found to be 1.1 eV.

To assign the electronic transitions observed with steady-state and transient absorption, we have performed DFT simulations of the band structure of FAPbBr₃, which is shown in **Figure 3a**. The valence band (VB) structure presents a two-fold degenerate VB1 and two quasi degenerate bands VB2, which are energetically separated by an energy difference of about 0.9 eV at the high symmetry point R. The two-fold degenerate first conduction band (CB1) is energetically separated from CB2 by about 1.5 eV. **Figure 3b** shows the total density of states (DOS) and the partial density of states (pDOS) of FAPbBr₃ calculated by DFT with the PBE functional, including spin-orbit coupling effects. VB1 is characterized by an equal contribution of Br 4p, Pb 6s and 6p orbitals, while VB2 presents a predominant Br 4p character. On the other hand, both the CB1 and CB2 show a prominent Pb 6p character.

Figure 3: (a) Band structure obtained at k-point path along Γ (0,0,0) \rightarrow R(1,1,1) \rightarrow T(0,1,1), (b) Total Density of states (DOS) and partial density of states (pDOS) for selected elements of FAPbBr₃ calculated by DFT with the PBE functional including spin-orbit coupling effects; (c) schematics of the band diagrams obtained by considering the experimental band gap and the theoretical energy differences taken at R point.

The theoretical band gap (VB1 \rightarrow CB1) value is ~ 0.9 eV, which is strongly underestimated as compared to the electronic bandgap obtained from the Elliott model (2.37 eV), as expected for this method of calculation which on the contrary predicts reliable values for the energy differences among the bands³⁹. In particular, the calculated energy differences VB1-VB2 and

CB1-CB2 are ~ 0.9 eV and ~ 1.5 eV, respectively. The scheme in **Figure 3c** shows the theoretical energy diagram of FAPbBr₃, where the electronic bandgap value has been substituted with the experimental one, obtained from the Elliot fit. **Table 1** summarizes these results also reporting the direct transition of the calculated FAPbBr₃ bands in the LDA approximation.

Transition at R point	Theoretical Transition Energy (eV)	Transition Energy (eV)	ΔE (eV)
VB1 \rightarrow CB1	0.9	2.37	--
VB2 \rightarrow CB1	1.8	3.27	+ 0.9
VB1 \rightarrow CB2	2.4	3.87	+ 1.5
VB2 \rightarrow CB2	3.3	4.77	+ 2.4

Table 1. The theoretical energy transition at the R point, the transition energy shifted to the experimental electronic bandgap, and the differences between the transition energy with respect to the VB1 \rightarrow CB1 transition (ΔE) are here reported.

In the light of this information, we discuss the valence band photoelectron spectrum of FAPbBr₃ reported in **Figure 4a**, obtained using a photon energy of 65 eV, that exhibits three different peaks centered respectively at the binding energy of 2.0, 3.1 and 4.4 eV. These peak values were obtained by fitting the experimental spectrum by using three gaussian functions (labeled as P1, P2, and P3 in the figure) and a Shirley background function⁴⁰. These features are assigned respectively to the first three VBs based on the valence band structure predicted by DFT calculations (see details in **Section S3** of SI). The pDOS of these calculations are shown in **Figure 4b** and **4c**, (shifted of 1.45 eV with respect to the valence

band maximum to be aligned with the experimental data) for Br 4p and in **Figure 4c** that of Pb 6s and Pb 6p, respectively. In the limit of this fitting approximation, the energy difference between VB1 and VB2 was estimated to be 1.1 eV, in very good agreement with the experimental TA spectrum (see **Figure 2**) and with the theoretical value of 0.9 eV (see **Figure 3c** and **Table 1**). In the light of the results obtained by optical measurements, photoelectron spectroscopy and DFT calculations, we assign the absorption structure at about 3.4 eV to the VB2→CB1.

Figure 4: (a) Experimental photoelectron spectra of the film of FAPbBr₃ (orange circles) and the relative fit of the peak P1 (blue line), P2 (green line) and P3 (red line) by Gaussian functions, the Shirley background (grey line) together with total fitting curve (dashed black line). (b) The calculated pDOS of Br 4p (blue line) and (c) Pb 6s (crimson line) and Pb 6p (green line).

The FTAS spectra give a detailed picture of the carrier dynamics in excitations involving VB1, CB1 and VB2. **Figure 5a** and **5b** show the TA spectra at selected time delays, using a pump energy of 2.50 eV (above the optical band gap) and 3.85 eV (above the VB2→CB1 transition), respectively. The fluence used was 50 $\mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$, resulting in a carrier density of $3.8 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for the pump at 2.50 eV and of $3.4 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for the pump at 3.85 eV. The carrier density estimation and the complete TA maps collected in the range of -1 to 300 ps time delays are reported respectively in **Section S4** and **S5** in the SI.

The TA spectra shown in **Figure 5a** and **5b** exhibit similar features: the PB1 signal at 2.30 eV due to the bleaching of the exciton and the PB2 signal at 3.40 eV due to the bleaching of the VB2→CB1 transition, the sharp positive Photoinduced Absorption (PA1) signal at lower energies and the broad PA2 at higher energies with respect to PB1. The PB signals are determined by the changes in electronic occupation, band gap renormalization (BGR) and exciton screening induced by the photoexcited carriers¹⁰. PB1 is related to the bleaching of the exciton absorption and of the VB1→CB1 transition that is excited at both pump energies and PB2 is generated when the system is excited at 3.85 eV, above the VB2→CB1 transition (see the scheme in **Figure 5c** and **d**). The PB2 signal is also present in the TA spectra acquired with a pump at 2.50 eV, an excitation energy below that of the VB2→CB1 transition, confirming that the transition at 3.40 eV shares a band with the gap transition, namely CB1. In this condition, the occupancy and the band filling of CB1 induced by the excitation at 2.50 eV of VB1→CB1 transition induces the bleaching (PB2) also for the VB2→CB1 transition at

higher energy (see the scheme in **Figure 5d**)⁴¹. Moreover, the PB1 signal obtained at 3.85 eV shows a broader shape and a longer high-energy tail due to the hot carriers excited by the excess of energy provided by the excitation³². The PA1 signal is found using both pump energies but exhibits a much different lifetime with respect to PA2. In particular, PA1 has a shorter lifetime when FAPbBr₃ is excited with the pump at 2.50 eV than when it is excited at 3.85 eV. This behavior is well known and is related to the BGR and to the thermal relaxation process of the hot-carriers^{31,42}. Thus, the higher the energy given to the system, the longer the lifetime of the PA1 signal. On the other hand, the PA2 is principally assigned to the change in refractive index induced by the photoexcitation^{31,42}.

In order to study the thermal relaxation (thermalization and cooling) of the carriers, we focus on the rise time of the PB signals under different excitation conditions: it becomes slower as the carrier density and/or the excitation energy increase^{31,42,43}. The fitting procedure of the rise time and the temporal dynamics on longer timescales are reported in **Section S6** of the SI. The temporal dynamics of the PB1 and PB2 signals with a pump energy of 2.50 eV and a carrier density of $3.8 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ are shown in **Figure 5e** and they have the same dynamics with a rise time constant of 60 fs, confirming that these two PB signals are related to transitions that share one band, namely CB1. Furthermore, the short rise time of the PB signals is compatible with the resonant excitation of the band gap at 2.50 eV, generating excited carriers with a low excess of energy that rapidly reach the bottom (top) of CB1 (VB1)³¹. On the other hand, the rise time dynamics of PB1 and PB2 present differences

when FAPbBr₃ is excited at 3.85 eV (see **Figure 5f**), i.e., an energy sufficient to excite both VB1→CB1 and VB2→CB1 transitions: PB1 signal is slower than PB2, showing a rise time constant of 250 fs and 160 fs, respectively. This different behavior is accounted for by a different thermal relaxation process that involves the excited carriers from VB1 and VB2 to CB1. In principle, the thermal relaxation of the electrons excited in CB1 from VB1 and VB2 should influence in the same manner the dynamics of the rise time of both PB1 and PB2 signals. If this does not happen, as suggested by the experimental data, it is necessary to discuss in more detail how the carrier distribution in the valence and conduction bands could influence the dynamics of the transient signals. The reason why one of the two transient signals is more or less sensitive to the dynamics of the excited carriers in the valence band (holes) or in the conduction band (electrons), could be related to a different distribution of the density of the states of the bands involved^{44,45}. For the VB1→CB1 transition, the density of states is very similar for both bands (see **Figure 3b**), suggesting that the dynamics of PB1 (rise and decay) is equally affected by the dynamics of both excited electrons and holes. On the other hand, the VB2→CB1 transition involves two bands with a remarkably different density of states. In particular, VB2 exhibits a density of states approximately an order of magnitude higher than CB1, as shown by DFT calculations (see **Figure 3b**). This is due to the fact that FAPbBr₃ has a denser DOS in the VB than in the CB since the VB is mainly composed of 4p orbitals of bromine (which is the most abundant atom), whereas the CB is mainly characterized by 6p orbitals of lead, resulting in many more

valence than conduction states⁴⁵. In other words, the dynamics of the PB2 signal should be more influenced by the thermal relaxation and energy distribution of the excited holes in VB2 than excited electrons in CB1, since the density of states, and consequently the occupation of the holes, is an order of magnitude greater than that of the electrons at the energies considered. The bleaching dynamics in PB2 is dominated by the hole dynamics. The physical nature of the PB signals in the transient spectra are discussed in detail in **Section S7** of SI.

Figure 5: TA spectra of FAPbBr₃ acquired at selected time delays (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5 and 2.0 ps) with the fluence of 50 $\mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$ and the pump photon energies (E_p) of (a) 2.50 eV and (b) 3.85 eV. The labels (PB1, PB2, PA1, PA2) used in the figure are explained in the text. The vertical dashed band covers the spectral range where the scattered pump light dominates over the white light probe. Scheme of band diagrams for VB1, VB2 and CB1 involved in the excitation at (c) 2.50 eV and (d) 3.85 eV. The grey area represents the states occupied by electrons, while the white area indicates occupation by the holes. Experimental data (scatter) and fitting curve (line) of the temporal dynamics obtained at E_p of (e) 2.50 eV and (f) 3.85 eV with a fluence of 50 $\mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$, for PB1 at probe energy of 2.30 eV (green) and PB2 at probe energy of 3.40 eV (blue).

To shed further light on these aspects, we have performed transient measurements as a function of pump fluence at 3.85 eV, with the aim of evaluating how the rise dynamics of PB1 and PB2 are affected by the excited carrier density. **Figure 6** reports the temporal dynamics of PB1 and PB2 acquired with the pump at 3.85 eV and at increasing carrier densities ($0.7 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $3.4 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $13 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). The experimental results show that as the carrier density increases, the rise time of PB1 slows down (see **Figure 6a**), due to a slower thermal relaxation process induced by the higher carrier density⁴⁶, as reported in **Table 2**. This behavior indicates that the dominant processes influencing the rise time in PB1 are the thermalization and cooling of carriers in VB1 and CB1. Notably, at low carrier density, the signal rises in less than 100 fs, suggesting rapid thermalization, while the contribution of

cooling during the rise time is minimal. Conversely, at high carrier density, the rise time is prolonged due to reduced cooling rates, commonly associated with a bottleneck effect^{47,48}.

Figure 6: Experimental data (scatter) and fitting curve (line) of the temporal dynamics obtained at the pump photon energy (E_p) of 3.85 eV and at the probe photon energy of 2.30 eV (green) and 3.40 eV (blue) obtained at the carrier density of 0.7, 3.4, and $13 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

On the other hand, the PB2 dynamics related to the $\text{VB2} \rightarrow \text{CB1}$ transition (see **Figure 6b**), gets faster as the excited carrier density increases, suggesting that a scattering or many-body process is taking place. In the light of what we have already discussed about the influence of the density of states on the transient signal, we can assign these dynamics to the excited holes in VB2. In fact, VB2 shows a quasi-flat band structure determining a localization near the band maximum of all the excited holes. Consequently, the hole-hole scattering is the preferential process rather than hole-phonon scattering that leads the excited holes to the top of VB2. Moreover, the quasi-flat band structure of VB2, characterized by its nearly constant energy levels, allows for a very rapid localization of excited holes near the band

maximum that remain in this condition of high internal energy for tens of picoseconds. In fact, the decay times of PB1 and PB2 after the first picosecond show an increase and a decrease with the same time constant of few picoseconds, respectively, that were assigned to a partial hole transfer from VB2 to VB1 (see **Section S8** in SI for further details). This demonstrates that the holes excited into VB2 remain at high energy for a relatively long time, without invoking any intervention of a bottleneck effect^{47,48}. Consequently, it implies that the generation of long-lived high-energy holes is feasible even at low carrier densities, typical of the working conditions of a solar cell, just exploiting the favorable electronic structure of the first valence bands of perovskites. These findings may stimulate novel approaches for the design and the optimization of transparent perovskite solar cells, by fine tuning light absorption, carrier generation, and charge extraction.

Pump Energy (eV)	Carrier density (10^{18} cm^{-3})	τ_{rise} (ps)	
		PB1	PB2
3.85	0.7	0.08±0.03	0.37±0.18
	3.4	0.25±0.02	0.16±0.02
	13	0.42± 0.02	0.08±0.02

Table 2. Rise times (τ_{rise}) of PB1 and PB2 at different carrier densities following the excitation of the sample with a pump at 3.85 eV.

In conclusion, in this work we have combined PES, FTAS, and DFT calculations to gain a detailed overview of the electronic structure and excited carrier dynamics of FAPbBr₃. In this way, a complete picture of the electronic transitions involved in the absorption of radiations in the UV-Vis energy range was given, estimating the exciton binding energy (40 ± 5 meV), the electronic band gap (VB1→CB1, 2.37 ± 0.01 eV) of FAPbBr₃ and assigning the broad peak at about 3.4 eV present in the absorption and transient spectra to the VB2→CB1 transition. In the light of these findings, the temporal dynamics of the carriers excited in the electronic bands involved in these transitions were investigated by using different excitation energies and carrier densities, observing a different trend for the transient signals associated to the VB1→CB1 (PB1) and VB2→CB1 (PB2) transitions. Specifically, whereas PB1 exhibits a slowdown in its rise time as the carrier density increases, conversely PB2 shows an acceleration that was attributed to the thermalization process experienced by the holes excited in VB2. This implies that the excitation of long-living high-energy holes is viable, even under low carrier densities as in the working condition of solar cells. These valuable insights pave the way for exploring novel strategies and design approaches to maximize the efficiencies and performances of perovskite-based solar cell devices.

Methods

Perovskite synthesis method

PL and FTAS experiments were performed on FAPbBr₃ layers deposited in a 1 mm thick glass. For PES measurements, perovskite was deposited on ITO conductive substrates (Kintec company, 1.1 mm thick, 10 Ω /sq of sheet resistance). Both substrates, ITO and glass, were first cut into square shapes of 2.5 x 2.5 cm and then washed with a sequential cleaning procedure in a soap (5% in volume) and water solution first, then in deionized water and finally in isopropanol through ultrasonic baths of 10 minutes in order to remove organic compounds and dust.

Before depositing the perovskite, the cleaned substrates were soaked under a UV-light treatment for 30 minutes to improve the surface wettability to obtain a good perovskite film deposition.

In a vial, 1.0 M FABr (Dyesol) and 1.0 M PbBr₂ (TCI) were dissolved in DMSO and left them stirring all night.

FAPbBr₃ deposition was performed under N₂ atmosphere. Substrates (ITO and glass) were first heated at 60°C, and then, 80 μ l of the perovskite solution was dropped on the surface and spin-coated at 4000 rpm for 20 seconds. The solvent quenching method was employed to raise the perovskite crystallization, and 200 μ l of ethyl acetate was dropped at 10 seconds after the initiation of the spin. The substrates were then annealed at 80 °C for 10 minutes.

Photoluminescence (PL)

The PL measurements were performed by exciting the sample at room temperature with a cw laser diode at 3.06 eV (405 nm) focused to a diameter of about 100 μm and at an excitation density of 100 mW/cm². The PL was dispersed in a 30 cm long monochromator with a 1200 grooves/mm grating and detected with a Peltier-cooled charge-coupled device camera.

Femtosecond Transient Absorption Spectroscopy (FTAS)

The experimental setup for FTAS measurements consists of an amplified femtosecond laser system (35 fs pulse duration, 1 kHz repetition rate, 4 W power centered at 800 nm) that generates the tunable pump pulses by using an optical parametric amplifier. The probe is a white light supercontinuum beam (360–780 nm/1.60–3.45 eV) generated by focusing 3 μJ of the 800 nm pulse into a rotating CaF₂ crystal. The pump and the probe beams are focused on the sample with a diameter of 200 μm and 150 μm , respectively. The delay time between the two is changed by modifying the optical path of the probe, resulting in an instrument response function of about 50 fs. More details on the experimental setup can be found elsewhere⁴⁹.

Density Functional Theory (DFT)

The Quantum Espresso code has been used for all the calculations⁵⁰. Starting from the available experimental structural data of FAPbBr₃⁵¹, we optimized its atomic structure

employing DFT calculations. The structure was fully relaxed until the force on each atom was less than 0.05 eV/Å. Here we used the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) functional⁵² to describe the exchange-correlation functional. The pseudopotentials used were the fully relativistic Optimized Norm-Conserving Vanderbilt Pseudopotential⁵³. The energy cutoffs of wave functions were set to be 100 Rydbergs. We sampled the Brillouin zone (BZ) of the cubic system using an 4x4x4 Monkhorst-Pack grid⁵⁴.

The Quantum-Espresso suite has been used to generate the Kohn-Sham (KS) eigenstates/values to obtain the quasi-particle band energies. The single-electron optical absorption spectra based on the DFT wavefunctions were calculated using the pw2gw package of Quantum Espresso. To match the theoretical data with the experimental optical transition, both KS quasi-particle energies and single electron optical transition have been rigidly shifted so that the theoretical and experimental conduction band energies correspond³⁹.

Photoelectron Spectroscopy (PES)

Photoelectron spectroscopy data were acquired at the VUV-Photoemission beamline (Elettra, Trieste) under ultra-high vacuum conditions at room temperature using a Scienta R-4000 electron analyzer. The photon energy and total energy resolution were set to 65 eV and 30 meV, respectively. The surface of the FAPbBr₃ films was sputtered by Ar ions with energy 500 eV for 5 minutes, in order to remove the surface contamination (oxygen and

adventitious carbon)⁵⁵. The energy scale of the spectra was referred to the Fermi level of the metallic sample holder in electrical contact with the FAPbBr₃ films.

Author contribution

A.D.C. and D.C. conceived the project. G.A., D.C., P.O.K., F.T., and A.P. performed the transient measurements. G.A. performed the analysis of the transient results with the help and supervision of D.C., S.T., and F.Mart.. G.A. performed the theoretical calculations. D.O. modeled and performed the evaluation of the Elliott Fit. P.M., P.M.S., V.M., D.C., S.T., and G.A. performed the photoelectron spectroscopy measurements. F.Matt. and J.B. synthesized the material. All experimental and theoretical results have been discussed among all the authors. D.C. and G.A. wrote the first draft of the manuscript and all authors contributed to writing, reviewing, and editing the manuscript to its final form.

Acknowledgment

We gratefully acknowledge financial support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101007084. We also thank Dr. Philippe Baranek for the valuable discussions on the theoretical approach here used.

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